

ISic2720

I.Sicily inscription 2720

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

marble (white)

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova,Valentina Mignosa

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance

Catacomb of S.Giovanni

Coordinates**Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa, Museum or catacomb Antiquarium

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Apparatus

Text after Griesheimer 1996

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645140

PHI 333387

Bibliography

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Griesheimer, M. 1996. Nouvelles inscriptions funéraires de la catacombe Saint-Jean. *Rivista di Archeologia Cristiana*. 72: 115-132. At 126 no.11 fig.11

Orsi, P. 1896. Gli scavi a S. Giovanni a Siracusa. *Römische Quartalschrift für christliche Alterthumskunde und für Kirchengeschichte*. 10: 1-59. At 13 no.8

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